

Impact of Kosi Project on the Socio-Economic Transformation in the Kosi Region, Bihar

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Anisha

Research Scholar
Department Of Geography
B.N.M. University
MadhepuraBihar, India

Abstract

The Kosi Project is India's one of the major multi-purpose river valley projects designed in 1954 to provide flood protection in Nepal terai and north-east Bihar plain apart from the control of excess silt discharge, check on westward transfer, provision of irrigation, generation of hydel power and above all, agricultural and rural reconstruction in a backward region of Bihar.

Kosi, a turbulent and disastrous river, called 'Sorrow of Bihar' brings floods every year and causes huge loss of property and lives. Due to shifting nature of the river, it has got notoriety. The project has helped a lot in bringing socio-economic change in the kosi Region.

Keywords

Project, Discharge, Turbulent, Disastrous, Notoriety, etc.

Introduction

The Kosi river known as the 'Sorrow of Bihar' attracted the attention of the Government as early as 1891, but no concrete steps were taken to harness the river until 1945. Disastrous floods were almost an annual feature, as not a single year passed without flood report or damage done to human settlements, people, livestock, their hearths and homes. The discussion regarding the feasibility of dams or dykes continued to preoccupy the minds of both the statesmen and engineers for long. The proposal mooted out could not materialize either due to difficult terrain of the upper catchment basin or to huge financial implications involved. The central water Irrigation and Navigation commission in 1946 proposed the construction of a 239 meter (783ft.) dam at Belka near Barah-kshetra with a reservoir to impound 41 sq. km. (6.9 million acre feet) of water, generation of 3.1 million KWH of cheap hydel power, a barrage at chatra, protective dykes and excavation of irrigation canals to feed 15.4 lakh ha. of land in Bihar and Nepal. This gigantic scheme was shelved in view of the huge cost of 177 crore of rupees as also because of seismological, silting, scouring and constructional problems to be faced apart from the doubtful efficacy of this ambitious project itself. If constructed, the Belka dam would have the world's highest concrete dam. The project plan prepared by CWPC in 1953 was modified before the kosi Project saw its beginning. Originally estimated to cost 95 crores of rupees, the current plan envisaged the construction of a masonry barrage 1149 m. long across the kosi at Hanuman Nagar in Nepal on the Bihar-Nepal border with two earthen embankments of over 120 km. each along the right and left banks with width between the two embankments varying from 5 to 16 km. to keep the kosi in check. The implementation of the project followed since 14th January 1955 with the construction of parallel embankments-the western one 124km. and the eastern one 146 km.

The Kosi Project is one of the major multi-purpose river valley projects designed in 1954 to provide flood protection in Nepal terai and north-eastern Bihar plain apart from the control of excess silt discharge, check on westerly translation, provision of irrigation, generation of hydel power and above all, agricultural and rural reconstruction in a backward region of Bihar. It covers an area of 16,615 km² and possesses 1 crore population. The Kosi region extends from 25⁰15'5" to 26⁰37'30" north latitudes and lies between 85⁰44'10" and 87⁰44'10" east longitudes. The Kosi region encompasses wholly or in part densely populated districts of Saharsa, Madhepura, Khagaria, Purnea, Katihar, Madhubani, Darbhanga, Samastipur and trans-gangetic Bhagalpur While Indo-Nepal border sets its northern limit, the Ganga river delimits its southern boundary.

Objective of study

The paper tries to investigate the setting of Kosi river project and its impact on overall socio-economic changes on the economy and society of the region .

Review of Literature

A major amount of research has been undertaken on the Kosi region as pertaining to its agriculture, irrigational potential and regional development. The works of Dr. E. Ahmad, Dr. P. Dayal, Dr. B.N Sinha, Dr. K.N. Das, Dr. K.K.L Das are noteworthy in this direction Dr. K.N. Das has worked on 'population and Landuse

changes in the Kosi region of Bihar.' B.N. Sinha has done his research on the land use changes of Kosi Basin. The articles written by Dr. G.N. Jha, G.P. Sinha, T.N. Sheshadri throw ample light on the theme Kosi is a turbulent river known as the 'Sorrow of Bihar' and as such, Government bulletins also describe the flood situation, its ravages and impact on the people and economy. After the construction of kosi barrage, much control has been witnessed, but still it is very mysterious to predict its nature because of its ever-changing course and damage incurred by floods every year.

Main Text**Study Area:****The Kosi : A Problem River**

To geologists, geographers and engineers, the kosi has remained an enigma owing to its difficult terrain and challenging physical and hydrological problems. The kosi only 965 km. long issues from 5490 m. high Tibetan plateau, north of the central chain of stupendous Himalayan peaks. The kosi catchment basin is drained by the seven streams (Sapt Kosi), viz. the Arun, sun, Tamur, Dudh, Bhotia, Tamba and the Indravati. The kosi drains a vast catchment area of 59.57 sq.km. which ranks next only to Indus and the Brahmaputra catchment areas. Apart from the incidence of high rainfall, the mighty Himalayan glaciers cause kosi's annual discharge of 5305 cubic metre near Barahshetra upstream of the chatra range. Near chatra, the flood water rises as high as 9 metres within 24 hours during peak monsoon storms (June-Sept). The kosi for these topographical and meteorological reasons is rated as one of the problem rivers of the world and is notorious for the rapidity of its stream, high silt discharge in the upper course and devastating floods in the lower basin. The area affected by floods in Bihar and Nepal works out to 21000 km². Kosi, which has earned the epithet of 'the sorrow of Bihar' used to devastate fertile agricultural land from 2400 to 3200 ha. besides affecting two million people. In addition to those, annual loss estimated in terms of money value works out to more than 10 crores of rupees.

Economic Malaise

There is a close link between the regional population and the carrying capacity of land, especially in an agrarian society where land is almost the sole support of the people. While the land is fixed in areal extent, population is increasing at a staggering rate of 2.5 percent and increasing numbers can be supported only if there is proportionate increase in agricultural production by a more intensive utilization of agricultural land and application of advanced technology. This calls for a constant process of adjustment and readjustment between people and their resources.

The economy of the region has been stagnating for a long time. Marked by traditional sedentary subsistence agriculture, lacking in mineral and basic industrial resources and beset with the vagaries of the capricious and devastating kosi, the region has been steadily declining in material well being. The growing pressure of population on land has sapped all available resources and has presented adequate investment over agriculture due to lack of capital formation, so necessary for building up development infrastructure in order that the agricultural economy is revitalised.

The Kosi Project, started on 14th January 1955 was designed to inject new life and vigour into the shattered economy of the command area. This is especially aimed at ameliorating the social condition and economic malady of a great majority of the people by stabilizing and improving agricultural and allied activities. It was an attempt to prevent menacing floods, providing irrigation and electricity and improve soil. The project has virtually changed the outlook of the people and has made it possible to use modern technology and scientific methods of farming. It has encouraged farmers to use manure and chemical fertilizer which was not possible before due to lack of irrigation, and to use better seeds, which thrive well with heavy fertilization and irrigation. With the harnessing of the kosi, better transport facilities are now available which make possible quicker dissemination of modern knowledge and provide better marketing facilities. The stabilization of agriculture has made it possible to develop rural industries, particularly agro-based industries, e.g. jute and Sugarcane with the help of hydel power of the kosi as well as thermal power developed at Barauni. Among other efforts worthy of mention which have infused a dynamic life in the regional economy are the efforts towards better land tenure apart from the construction and expansion of the Barauni industrial complex which is situated not far from the region.

Irrigation Potential

The chief ailment of the agricultural economy of the lower basin has been the disorganization of agricultural water supply resulting from the floods and vagaries of the kosi. Above all, two things are needed to stabilize its agriculture firstly freedom from floods, and secondly, assured agricultural water supply during dry summer and cold winter months. Irrigation, therefore, received top priority next to flood control in the project. Through a network of main branches, distributaries and village channels, the canal system will provide an all-round irrigation to a large area.

Impact on Regional Economy

The chief aim of the project has been to confine the river in a permanent course, to arrest excess discharge of harmful silt and sand as well as to check further westward translation of the river to ensure agricultural water supply to the needy lands, to increase general fertility of soils, provide cheap hydroelectricity to villagers as well as to numerous agro industries i.e. sugar mills, jute mills, rice, pulse, flour mills etc. Which are likely to be restored or opened in the region. The region, once the most affected part of the state on account of vagaries of the kosi, its consequent high floods and colossal economic loss and which hitherto remained a cinderella of hydrological studies will, on final completion turn to be one among the most economically developed and prosperous parts of the country. The people in general will reap the fruits of the project, and majority among the working force will be absorbed in various employment opportunities provided by the project. A major breakthrough in the field of agriculture has been achieved in Purnea and Saharsa districts and hopes of economic development are just around the corner.

Conclusion

The regional personality of this historically, socially and economically backward area bears an indelible mark of the kosi-'Sorrow of Bihar'. The command area is undergoing a process of development at a steady pace with the inception of the project.

By and large, life of the people in the entire lower basin has begun to change and fruits of development are slowly but surely percolating into the socio-economic fabric of the society. If all the projected features of the project are completed fully and socio economic progress in the region guided properly, there is no reason why the traditional bound agrarian system does not catch up with technological changes taking place in other parts of the country. The project has greatly modified the physical environment in the basin and it is now the turn of the people of the region to play their part if they wish to raise themselves from the slough of poverty and want, and desire prosperous future for the posterity. Radical transformation for rural uplift is already taking place and if this is based on scientific appraisal of landuse capabilities, it is likely to be more profitable for great majority of the rural people residing in the kosi command area.

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